

Data Management Plan: State of the science on plastic chemicals – Identifying and addressing chemicals and polymers of concern (PlastChem project)

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This data management plan (DMP) was created using easy.DMP (<https://easydmp.sigma2.no>).

Project summary

Despite plastics being widely used in and highly relevant for societies, the knowledge base on their chemical composition and the impacts of plastic chemicals on humans and the environment is fragmented. Accordingly, an authoritative resource that enables evidence-based policy development to better protect public health and nature is missing. The PlastChem project will produce such resource in form of a high-quality state-of-the-science review that synthesizes the scientific evidence on hazardous substances in plastics and prioritize these chemicals and the polymers they are contained in.

To achieve this, the project will consolidate information on >15 000 plastic chemicals from existing databases, polymer mass flows, scientific and market data to systematically compile hazard and exposure information on chemicals and polymers. The resulting PlastChem database will be used to group plastic chemicals according to structure and to prioritize groups of chemicals using a weight-of-evidence approach, considering hazard, exposure, and market data. The priority chemicals will be linked to the polymers they are contained in based on empirical evidence (i.e., detection in plastics). In addition, we will evaluate the leachate toxicity of all chemicals released from plastic products, thus, including unknown chemicals and mixture effects. To ensure policy relevance, we will assess and prioritize policy needs in close collaboration with the advisory board and other experts. This interaction will also guide the project implementation and ensure that the review is tailored to the policy needs.

The PlastChem review and database as main project outputs will be authoritative resources for developing policies that promote a non-toxic environment in line with the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability and the global plastic treaty.

Data summary

Purpose of the data collection/generation

The purpose of the data collection and generation in the PlastChem project is to produce a state-of-the-science review of the scientific evidence on hazardous substances in plastics. Specifically, the review will

- provide a comprehensive overview of all plastic chemicals,
- identify groups of chemicals of concern and link those to the polymers and products they are used in,
- prioritize chemicals and polymers based on hazard, exposure, and market information,
- summarize mass-flow information for polymers to guide regulatory action to specific areas,
- synthesize the compiled scientific evidence to assess and prioritize the regulatory needs.

Types, origin, formats, and size of the data

The types, origin, formats, and expected size of the data collected and generated in the PlastChem project are summarized in Table 1.

Data utility

The data collected and generated in the PlastChem project can be used by

- researchers studying chemicals in plastics, in particular their chemical analysis in products and the environment, their hazards to human health and the environment, and their replacement by safer alternatives,
- regulatory experts in the public and private sector to assess specific (groups of) chemicals in plastics or develop management measures to eliminate or minimize chemicals of concern,
- decisionmakers in the public and private sector to develop policies, processes, and practices that eliminate or minimize plastic chemicals of concern to protect human health and the environment.

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Table 1. Overview of the types, origin, formats, and expected size of the data collected and generated in the PlastChem project.

WP	Type of data	Contributor*	Origin of data	Format	Expected size	Availability
1	PlastChem database of all chemicals known to be used in plastics for each entry (unique chemical): - chemical identifiers (InChI keys, INChI strings, CAS registry numbers, SMILES) - chemical name (IUPAC) and synonyms - molecular formula - function (categorical) - polymer (categorical) - sector (categorical) - food contact (yes/no/unknown) - other chemical properties - origin of data (categorical)	NGI	Seven databases of plastic chemicals (Aurisano db, CPPdb, ECHA PMFC, FCCdb, FCCmigex, LitChem, PlasticMAP)	xlsx, csv	50 MB	Publicly available of Zenodo
1	Hazard data Hazard classification according to CLP and other sources for each entry (unique chemical): - carcinogens, mutagens, and reproductive toxicants (CMRs) - specific target organ toxicity (STOT) - endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDC) - acute/chronic aquatic toxicity - persistence, bioaccumulation, and mobility (PBT, vPvB, PMT, vPvM)	NTNU, NGI	15 regulatory inventories	xlsx, csv	50 MB	Publicly available of Zenodo as part of the PlastChem database
1	Exposure data for selected entries - production volume (numerical) - marketed for use (yes/no) - detection in plastics (yes/no) - polymer type of use or detection (categorical)	NTNU	Previous databases	xlsx, csv	50 MB	Publicly available of Zenodo as part of the PlastChem database
1	R codes for constructing the PlastChem database	NGI, NTNU	Own work	R code	50 MB	Github
1	Overview of mass-flow analyses and market data - tabulated summary of available mass-flow analyses (free text) - production and sales volume, function and use data for selected polymer types	NGI, Empa	Scientific literature, market reports	xlsx, csv	50 MB	Internal use

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1	Leachate toxicity data - polymer analyzed (categorical) - product analyzed (categorical) - bioassay type (categorical) - endpoint type (categorical) - effect observed (yes/no/unclear) - effect level or concentration (numerical)	EAWAG	Scientific literature	xlxs, csv	50 MB	Publicly available on Zenodo in conjunction with the publication of results
2	Grouping of chemicals - group classifier associated with chemical in the PlastChem database	Empa	Own analyses	csv	10 MB	Publicly available of Zenodo as part of the PlastChem database
2	Assessment and prioritization of plastic chemicals and major groups of plastic chemicals - narrative assessment	all	Scientific literature, review of reviews, own analyses	Text	-	Part of the public state-of-the-science review
2	Assessment and prioritization framework for polymers of concern	NTNU, NGI	Own analyses	Text	-	Part of the public state-of-the-science review
3	Alignment with other reports - summary of available reports on plastic chemicals	FPF, Empa	Summary of main concepts and topics	Text	-	Part of the public state-of-the-science review
3	Expert consultations - interview transcripts and minutes	FPF	Experts	Text	50 MB	Internal use
3	Assessment of policy needs - narrative assessment	all	Own analyses, previous reports, expert input	Text	-	Part of the public state-of-the-science review
4	State-of-the-science review on plastic chemicals - narrative synthesis of the data mentioned above	all	All of the above	Text, figures, tables	20 MB	Publicly available on Zenodo

* Note: EAWAG (Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science and Technology), Empa (Swiss Federal Laboratories for Materials Science and Technology), FPF (Food Packaging Forum Foundation), NGI (Norwegian Geotechnical Institute)

FAIR Data

Metadata

We will document and provide the following metadata accompanying the data collected and created in the PlastChem project

Database creation

- sources of parent databases
- sources of hazard information
- code for database compilation, consolidation, and clean-up

Grouping of chemicals

- sources of curated lists of chemical groups
- information on other grouping tools

Assessment of chemical groups and polymers

- scoring and prioritization system

The data collected and created in the PlastChem project will be open by default. All database versions, including relevant metadata and documentation, will be made publicly available on Zenodo. The assessments of chemical groups and polymers conducted in the project, including a detailed description of the methodology, will be openly available as part of the state-of-the-science review on Zenodo. No specific tools, conditions or methods are required to access the data.

The PlastChem database will be stored as files in Microsoft Excel and comma-separated values (csv) format which is accessible with a wide array of software. The use of multiple chemical identifiers (CAS registry numbers, InChI keys, InChI strings, SMILES) will ensure that that chemicals in the database are easily identified. IUPAC names will be provided as standard vocabulary for chemical naming.

The data uploaded to Zenodo and in the state-of-the-science review will be provided under a Creative Commons Attribution Non Commercial 4.0 International license without embargo. The data will be available as long as Zenodo decide to host them.

Allocation of resources

The costs for implementing this data management plan are covered by the project. Martin Wagner will be responsible for the data management in the project. The long-term preservation of the data is ensured by the data deposition on Zenodo. Alternatives to this are the Norwegian repository DataverseNO which provides similar services.

Data security

Before publication of the data on Zenodo, all data will be stored on a shared cloud folder using NTNU's instance of Microsoft OneDrive. All project partners will have access to this folder using a secure Microsoft login. In addition, regular backups will be performed automatically using an external hard drive. Should data be stored locally, all project partners are instructed to follow procedures that fully ensure data security.

Ethical aspects

The project will not collect or create sensitive or proprietary data. Accordingly, no ethical or legal issues are foreseen.

Other issues

No other issues relevant to our data are foreseen.